

Remote Laboratories for Engineering Education

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Abstract. In engineering education, laboratories are important academic resources as they provide practical training in addition to the fundamental theories. However, advanced tools, costly equipment and machinery imply a large investment that only a limited number of institutions can afford. The rapid Internet development and the advent of IoT (Internet of Things) have provided new possibilities and challenges for designing and deploying remote collaborative learning systems. Web-based online experimentation turns to be a key feature in deploying digital solutions in engineering education.

This work proposes a collaborative digital platform to perform remote activities such as data visualization, control, monitoring, algorithm implementation and real-time programming of the remote machinery and equipment. An open architecture encompassing the embedded hardware, the intermediate data broker and the Front-End remote access allows new possibilities for applied research and education. Thereby, the remote students and researchers may have access to control and monitor the real research equipment and laboratories, not locally available. The idea to expand and improve education and research in engineering fields by providing remote access to infrastructure, equipment, resources and data leads to substantial benefits for science and economy.

Keywords: Remote Laboratories, Collaborative Platform, Online Tools.

1 Introduction

In engineering education, laboratories represent an important academic resource as they provide practical training in addition to the fundamental theories. However, the acquisition of new machinery and the maintenance of the equipment imply a large investment that only a limited number of universities can afford. With the advent of IoT (Internet of Things), one requires more access to the remote infrastructure to be able to do data visualization, system monitoring, algorithm implementation and distance programming [1]. Web-based online experimentation turns to be a key feature in deploying digital education solutions in engineering education. It offers a tremendous opportunity to add flexibility in traditional curricula by providing students with versatile access to the learning material from both a time and location perspective [2,3].

The existing remote labs platforms designed for education issues are not always suitable to carry out education and research activities in a free and widespread way, due to some limitations in data communication or the user interface. For example, the students' interactions with remote equipment are often limited to change only the system configuration, the controller parameters, the setpoints and to collect and analyze the data on their computer [4,5].

Therefore, the user Web-based interface of our remote platform developed at University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland has been upgraded to offer an additional textual programming environment and code sharing tools for distance programming of the machines and laboratory devices [6].

This paper presents a digital platform for online education activities through a collaborative widespread network deploying remote laboratories in electrical, mechanical and control engineering at a large scale within e-learning infrastructure and MOOC infrastructures. The collaborative platform is proposed to perform remote activities such as data visualization, monitoring, algorithm implementation and real-time programming of the remote machinery and equipment, used in engineering applications.

2 Objectives

This work permits to establish an institutional cooperation for an enhanced joint education and research activities as well as technology transfer, within UN sustainable development goals. The following general objectives are addressed to improve education and research in engineering fields:

- Developing and implementing innovative and collaborative activities through a Web-based remote laboratories platform within digital technologies, e-learning environments and MOOC infrastructures,
- Enhancing pedagogical and student-centred learning and teaching methodologies through remote experimental activities,
- Reducing costs of laboratories in higher education by sharing the available infrastructures, resources and laboratory equipment for a large-scale use in engineering education.

3 Infrastructure

The proposed infrastructure illustrated in figure 1 is composed of:

- 1) Laboratory devices fully equipped with different sensors, actuators and real-time embedded controllers. Controllers of National Instruments are used with FPGA and CPU modules, IO modules and Ethernet connection allowing remote operations as well as live video streaming. As test infrastructure, a pool of several

laboratory equipment is available such as electrical motors, moveable photovoltaic panels for sun tracking or other didactic laboratory experiments.

- 2) A common gateway interface offering standard telecommunication protocols (WebSocket) with secure data transmission between the local infrastructure and the remote users/programmers [7]. Communication between the Web interface and the remote system and the local controller includes real-time communication channels for operations such as start/stop the system, real-time data visualization, send commands as well as algorithms to be transferred in terms of source code.
- 3) A lab server for monitoring the system access and usage history to be aware of the connected devices which should be reached behind firewalls and without custom network configuration.
- 4) A Web-based Interface offering online control and monitoring panel which connects the users/programmers to the remote infrastructure. The Web interface proposes a user-friendly interface with live video streaming of the test site and data acquisition. The Web interface contains remote interactive tools to implement services such as:
 - Data sharing, data processing and data saving
 - Remote control and monitoring and data visualization
 - Distance programming of labs equipment
 - System modeling and control algorithms development
- 5) E-learning hosting environment: The Web-based SPA (Single Page Application) with data visualization, live video streaming, programming environment and control of the remote devices are integrated in a MOOC platform.

Fig. 1. Remote infrastructure composed of laboratory devices, local controllers, bidirectional data transfer, lab server, Web-based interface with different interactive digital tools.

4 Communication and security aspects

In remote engineering, communication protocols are open and give the freedom to develop innovative solutions. Learning platforms are not standardized to a level which would permit an easy migration. Therefore, in our remote experimentation setup, effort has been put mostly on the remote experiment and client-side tools with data under the direct control of the client rather than based on cloud storage.

The connection between the remote users and the server connected to the lab experiments must be secured against malevolent actors. The lab experiments and the server computer must be protected against unauthorized connection attempts which could steal resources, impair their usage by the users they are destined to, and possibly damage them by submitting repeated extreme commands. Also, the user computers should be protected against malware, phishing attempts, or any content which would tarnish the lab institution. And the experimental data integrity should be guaranteed to ensure users can rely on their remote experiment outcome.

On the remote labs side, server is connected to wired network which is difficult to attack. The weakest side is the client computers and their Internet access: Wi-fi connections have become the norm on laptops and tablets, and the security of public Wi-fi access points is often low or impossible to assess. To improve overall security, the use of TLS (SSL) encryption has become prevalent (HTTPS URLs), with more and more restrictions enforced to discourage practices known to be easily abused. Modern browsers flag pages served without encryption as unsecure, refuse unencrypted auxiliary resources accessed from encrypted pages “mixed content”, and remember if a site has been served via HTTPS to not switch back to unencrypted HTTP in future accesses (“HTTP Strict-Transport-Security”). The different digital tools are served from a server implemented in LabVIEW to the users’ browsers via HTTP (a simple request/reply protocol where the connection is closed after one or a few requests) and WebSocket [7], a lasting bidirectional stream of messages starting with an HTTP handshake. Both are supported natively by browsers. For the reasons described above, the encrypted versions of these protocols are used: HTTPS and WSS [7]. On WebSocket, messages are encoded in JSON [8], a good compromise between legibility and conciseness which is supported natively in browsers and elsewhere.

5 Interactive tools

With the evolution of technologies involved in remote experiments, the remote environment and digital tools have been improved very significantly. On the remote user side, mostly for security reasons, Java applets, Flash Player applications, and other native browser plugins have been replaced by JavaScript Web applications.

This chapter presents the developed tools for control, monitoring, data processing as well as remote programming of distant laboratory equipment via Web browser.

5.1 Control, monitoring and data visualization tools

As shown in figure 2, different interactive tools are proposed in a Web-based user interface to avoid any installation for the remote users. The Front-End interface allows the following features:

- Device On/Off
- Open-loop mode
- Closed-loop mode with choice of controllers (PID, State-space control, ...)
- Control and monitoring of system inputs (setpoints, controller parameters)
- Data visualization and saving
- Webcam live video

Fig. 2. Web-based control and monitoring panels (HTML) of smart devices in Open-loop and Closed-loop modes.

Control parameters and measurement data are sent as numbers and the video stream is sent as JPEG images in the same HTML interface, the easiest way to ensure synchronization between video and real-time signal traces.

The image transmission rate is 10 images per second. As for the data transmission rate, the data packages of 200 numbers, with acquisition rate of 500 microseconds, are sent every 100 milliseconds. Based on these data and images rates, the video quality suits well its purpose as a direct way to assess the system functioning.

5.2 Remote programming and code sharing

In addition, the HTML interface allows algorithms programming by means of a textual code editor. As our laboratory devices are equipped by means of the National Instruments controllers (MyRIO, CRIO), the code inserted in the Web interface must be only in the Python programming language. Nowadays, the Python language is progressively used for system scripting, Web development as well as software and algorithms development.

To achieve this aim, the method “SendPythonScript” has been developed in order to create a .py file and to paste the Python source code in it. This method calls the LabVIEW VI “System Exec” to compile and execute the Python code, directly on the National Instruments controllers. The LabVIEW VI “System Exec” needs the name of the file with the .py extension to compile and run the Python source code. The final file is executed on the Real-time Linux operation system.

Once the Python file is compiled, compilation status, errors or warnings are sent back to the remote user via the HTML interface.

For variable transfer between Python and LabVIEW a bidirectional Socket communication is used. “CRIO to Python” is used to forward the real measurements to Python and to transfer them to the remote user. “Python to CRIO” is used to send the parameters and commands from the remote user to the controller. To ensure a high-speed data acquisition with the Hardware, the FPGA module of the controller is employed.

Figure 3 shows the five steps to follow in the Web interface to upload codes on the National Instrument controllers, by using a simple code editor. After selecting the “Programming” Tab (1) and clicking on the button “Edit” (2), a Pop-up window appears for inserting the code script in Python (3).

Few seconds after uploading the code (4) on the remote controller, the programming environment provides feedbacks such as compilation status, errors or warnings, or results of calculation (5).

Fig. 3. Web-based user interface for distance programming.

It takes between 1 to 3 seconds to transfer and compile the code and receive the compilation status on the Web interface. A sampling period of 2 to 3 milliseconds is required, for example to run the Python source code of a PID (Proportional–Integral–Derivative) controller on the CPU. The sampling period may be reduced by using a more efficient and faster processor or by optimizing the algorithms.

Finally, if one needs to use other programming languages such as C or Matlab, they should be first converted to Python, before inserting in the code editor. For this purpose, different converters such as SMOP (Simple Matlab/Octave to Python) or many other C to Python converters may be used.

6 Integration in learning platforms

A good integration of the interactive tools in learning platforms is important to give students an efficient learning experience. At University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland, the interactive remote tools are integrated within Moodle Platform as MOOCs.

Each MOOC offers several video clips where teachers explain the theory and what is expected from the students during the lab session. In addition, PDF files describe the theory, outline the remote infrastructure to be used and the different steps to carry out the remote laboratory. Different learning scenarios and pedagogical contents split into theoretical, experimental and evaluation phases lead the student during the laboratory session.

Real-time interaction over the Internet should enable students to efficiently interact with physical distance equipment, as an efficient interaction provides them with the

best possible feedback to minimize drawbacks inherent to the distance, with sufficient information to reproduce the state of the distant equipment and its operational conditions. Based on pedagogical contents, students can get orientation on their own, as well as to determine and elaborate adequate learning methods for new competences and skills.

Figure 4 shows the contents of a MOOC with subspaces corresponding to weekly activities, short videos, a set of offline exercises and numerical questions (quiz form) as well as the interactive control panels for online experimentation on movable solar panels located at university campus in Sion, Switzerland.

Fig. 4. A MOOC for online remote experimentation of movable solar panels at University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland, in Sion City.

7 Implementation and results

The remote labs activities have been implemented as several MOOCs in the e-learning platform of the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland. They are fully dedicated to hands-on activities for second-year students of Bachelor program in mechanical and electrical engineering.

The learning scenario of each lab session of approximately 3 hours is split into short videos describing how to use the various tools (experiment description, theoretical development, remote control panels, ...). A set of offline exercises and a set of numerical questions (quiz form) allow to validate students finding on the real laboratory infrastructure and to evaluate their understanding.

The platform has been extensively used during the COVID-19 crisis by engineering students at our university to carry out laboratory activities at home during the confinement period. Since Covid-19 pandemic, nearly half of the laboratories of some courses such as “Mechatronics” and “Control systems” are carried out remotely.

The students can freely carry out the laboratory session on the remote labs infrastructure on the university campus or at home. As the number of each remote laboratory equipment is limited (for example 8 DC motors, 8 Ball systems, ...), if two students want to use the same device at the same time, FIFO (First In - First Out) policy will apply. This means the first user stays in controller mode and the other users pass in observer mode until the waiting time is ended. The waiting time can be set based on the number of users and available remote labs.

The MOOCs as well as all the remote laboratory infrastructures are also available to other engineering schools. Thus, every student enrolled in the MOOC may have access to the educational resources and remote labs facilities.

For evaluating the students’ satisfaction of the different MOOCs on the remote laboratories, each MOOC session is followed by an evaluation survey. As a matter of fact, the students’ feedbacks are one of the most significant indicators in both face-to-face and online educational activities. The course evaluation survey includes different questions such as concept, remote laboratory facilities, Web connection, learning materials, student involvement, learning outcomes, time, workload, etc. The survey data are used to improve the different pedagogical contents, documents and resources and to update the laboratory infrastructure and to enhance their Web-based interface and control panels.

8 Comparison with other remote labs platforms

Remote infrastructures have emerged as a good alternative to the traditional in-person laboratories in engineering education. They allow engineering students and researchers to experiment with real hardware and equipment remotely, from anywhere with an internet connection. In comparison with other similar existing remote solutions [2,3,9,10], our platform offers the following advantages:

- Secure Web access and data transfer
- User-friendly Web interface
- No required third-party software or licenses to be installed
- Remote controlling and monitoring, allowing time plots with logging features
- Textual programming and code sharing environment for distance programming

The main weakness of the developed platform is the lack of troubleshooting and remote debugging. To be able to carry out remote maintenance and online problem solving, our platform needs some more hardware and software developments.

Another disadvantage is the limited number of remote laboratory equipment at our school. From time to time, students should stay several minutes in waiting list (FIFO) until a remote device is available for experimenting. A potential solution to this problem can be a booking system to manage all the remote labs and users.

9 Conclusion

The increasing use of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) had, has, and will have various impacts on academic institutions and the daily work of students, teachers and researchers. Currently, the remote education and research methodologies are rapidly progressing, and as more users utilize the remote possibilities, the knowledge and technology around remote approaches will improve [11,12]. This will empower more digital skills, faster and more reliable telecommunication services as well as new programs and applications with a better understanding of their characteristics.

This work promotes different issues through a Web-based collaborative digital platform for engineering applications with low requirements for deployment and operation. We can mention secure Web access and data transfer with no required third-party software or licenses, remote access for controlling and monitoring of engineering equipment, user-friendly Web interface with live video and data acquisition, fluid data visualization allowing time plots with logging features, full system security, digital tools such as data sharing, data processing and data saving, textual Web programming environment and code sharing tools for distance programming of labs equipment.

Furthermore, the idea to expand and improve education and research in engineering fields by providing remote access to infrastructure, equipment, resources and data leads to substantial benefits for science and economy [13]. In fact, the developed remote platform offers the engineers to share their experience, expertise and resources as well as to connect and to collaborate more efficiently, a key characteristic of science literacy. As for economic impact, one can mention reducing costs of laboratories and research equipment in higher education by sharing the available infrastructure, resources and equipment for use in engineering fields.

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